

Investigating Experience Design in Industry

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Abstract: In this paper, the field of experience design is investigated in industry with the aim to identify research opportunities that can advance experience design as a practice. To this end, seven interviews were held with design consultancy agencies. The focus was to discover common practices and unmet needs in relation to experience related aspects of design. Some of the topics included; client demands, end-user involvement, quality standards and community building. Results showed that common practices and unmet needs could be grouped into four themes that involve (1) the constituents of experience design, (2) processes involved (3) expertise needed to design for experience and (4) aspects related to experience design clients. The paper is concluded with a list of research opportunities aimed to advance experience design as a practice.

Key words: experience, design, industry, practice, research, innovation.

1. Introduction

Experience design is a developing field of design. Its aim is to optimize people's experiences of products, systems, services and brands [1,2]. Typical experience design projects cross multiple design disciplines such as product design, communication design and architecture. In retail for instance, lighting, spatial layout, store fixtures, product packaging and interactive media are all involved in creating a unified customer experience [3,4]. Experience design - which explicates subjectivity in design - relates to the discourse on user experience [5], product experience [6] and emotional design [7,8].

The aim of this study is to investigate common practices and unmet needs regarding experience related aspects of design in order to advance experience design as a practice. Governmental programs (regional, national as well as European) have been set-up to drive innovation by connecting industry with academia. In this line of thinking, we want to take current practices in industry as starting point and extrapolate them to research and educational activities in academia. Seven design consultancy agencies [9-15] were interviewed about experience related aspects of design, which is coined experience design. Some of these questions included; the manner in which experience is defined within their practices; how they dealt with experience during the design and research process; the disciplines and types of expertise needed and which types of questions from business favor an experience design approach.

2. Method

2.1. Participants

Seven companies participated in this study (Table 1): Bright Innovation [9] is a design consultancy agency. This agency specializes in the fields of medical design, green technology and consumer electronics. They conduct design research and apply design thinking into the areas of business, marketing and engineering. Sparckl [10] is a company providing services that allow people to design experiences for others. In their practice emphasis is given to the application of gaming principles in service design. Informaat [11] is a user experience design agency with over 20 years of experience in making information systems useful and usable. Their clients are financial organizations and government. Design projects at Informaat are usually significant and involve multiple disciplines. Premsele [12] is a Dutch governmental platform for design and fashion. Premsele aims to improve the cultural climate for design in the Netherlands. They pursue this goal through the production of lectures, debates, exhibitions, research and publications in the Netherlands and abroad. Opera [13] is an environmental design agency for three-dimensional communicative environments including retail design, interior design, and exhibit design. Clients include, government, industry, healthcare and museums. Senta [14] is a marketing consultancy agency having specialized in multi-sensory experience i.e., 5D-marketing. Clients include retail, finance and (semi) government. Frog design [15] is an innovation firm having eight studios around the globe. Clients include original equipment manufacturers (OEM's), service providers in the (tele) communications industry, professional B2B software and medical systems.

Table 1. Description of the participating companies

Company name	Type of service	Primary fields of application
Bright Innovation	Design consultancy	Green technological, medical and consumer electronics
Sparckl	Service design	Entertainment and e-health
Informaat	User experience design	Financial and governmental
Premsele	Design institute	Societal awareness and education
Opera	Exhibition design	Cultural and retail
Senta	Marketing consultancy	Financial services and consumer products
Frog Design	Global innovation	OEM's and telecommunication services

2.2. Procedure and analysis

The interviews took two to three hours were held at the design consultancy agencies of the interviewees. The interview was semi-structured using actively listening combined with elaborate note taking. These notes were written out in full after the interview. A phenomenological reduction i.e., a technique used in qualitative research [16] performed upon these notes resulted in a closed coding schema consisting of 14 labels. Interviewees' expressions were coded and grouped, leading to the emergence of the four themes described below. Expressions that were highly illustrative for a specific topic within a theme were quoted.

3. Results

The interviews resulted in four main themes. The first theme, labeled experience design constituents, involves the accumulation of different definitions of experience design given by the interviewees as well as different perceived values of experience design for industry and society. The second theme, labeled experience design process, involves methods and tools used in relation to experience design. The third theme, labeled experience design expertise, involves various design disciplines mentioned by the interviewees as well as the design

expertise needed to design for experience successfully. The fourth and last theme, labeled experience design clients, involves clients' awareness of experience design and activities that design agencies setup to promote this awareness. This paper ends with the accumulation of the overall findings into a list of activities, which are believed to advance experience design practice and can further be used to initiate research and education within academic settings. The results of these interviews and the activities that accumulated from them do not reflect absolute notions but involve shared insights that are aimed to reveal directions for industry academia cooperation.

3.1. Experience design constituents

This theme involves the constituents of experience design. Topics range from the contextual and individual forces at play when designing for experience, the role of the designer as mediator for end-users and other stakeholders, the bodily bases of experience and the intrinsic and instrumental values attached to an experience design approach. The topics are listed in Table 2 and are described in more detail below.

(1) **Context.** When designing for experience one should consider all aspects of a context that can affect it. As one interviewee expressed it in relation to product design, "experience involves everything around a product, from the moment one hears about it, when appropriated in everyday life, until it is put aside or updated [15]" or as another person stated, "experience involves the relationship between product, person and environment [9]" that in relation to retail includes "personnel, spatial layout and product-assortment [14]." Also, one interviewee expressed that given the availability of services on mobile computing platforms; a service can be used "in different social situations, on different times of day and in different physical locations [10]", which changes the experience of a service.

(2) **Narrative.** The second topic focuses on designing for experience as a narrative. It is not purely the formal qualities of a design producing the experience but a person integrating these formal qualities into a narrative. As one participant described in relation to user interface design "user experience lies in the process of using interface elements rather than in the actual elements themselves [11]" and from an exhibition design perspective the experience is a narrative, "which is created by moving between physical spaces [13]". Products can also be regarded as narrative since they will be adopted in "people's daily rituals [9,15]" and thus given personal meaning. This meaning can differ between individuals but as one person noted "this meaning should be designed explicitly, although one cannot control it completely [12]."

(3) **Democratic.** The third theme, which is labeled democracy, involves the relationship between designers, clients and end-users. Oftentimes a more equal relationship between these parties is mentioned. One interviewee expressed that design in general is such a complex activity that a democratic approach towards designing is essential. "Problems have different owners. Thus, solutions to these problems can be regarded as integrating various viewpoints (e.g., organizational, individual, technological and commercial) [12]." With respect to service design, an interviewee mentioned that, "many points of feedback are implemented in a service hereby allowing continuous monitoring of service quality by end-users during and after realization [10]". When enabling such democratic process in design "trust and understanding between parties is very important [12]."

(4) **Engagement.** Experience design involves engaging people's bodily sensitivities. As one interviewee commented for exhibition design, "to engage visitors in an exhibition, clear communication is required [13]." This engagement may be sensory, as mentioned for household products and dining establishments [14], socially as mentioned for computing artifacts and exhibitions [12,13] and behaviorally as

mentioned for IT products [15]. However, this engagement can also be manifested in an emotional and cognitive level. As one interviewee expressed it, “moods and emotions lie within a person but are affected by interacting with design [11].” and another interviewee mentioned, “design involves the symbolic relationship between people and material [12]” Engagement may be typified as ‘soft’ when it has an atmospheric character and ‘hard’ when it has a attentive character, requiring people’s response [13].

(5) **Respect.** The fifth theme involves respect for end-users. Two interviewees stated that quality judgments should be made by people themselves (i.e. end-users) and not by an external authority [12,15]. This requires careful observation of people’s “real needs and desires [10]” and is promoted in design practice by “placing precedence to the opinions of end-users in relation to other stakeholders [11].” Many interviewees expressed a concern for people’s wellbeing and empowerment illustrated by the following quotes: ”As a designer you want to touch people’s minds and hearts [11]”, “create enjoyable experiences [10]”, “create bonds like friendships; trustworthy with an element of surprise [14]” but also “allowing people to grow, learn and discover [10]” and “let people do things they could not do before [15].”

(6) **Strategic.** Experience design involves aligning experiences with instrumental goals (e.g., monetary and behavioral). In general, companies such as original equipment manufacturers (OEM’s) and service providers are aware that respecting the values and preferences of end-users can advance their businesses. For instance, return on investment and market share can be increased by creating products that fit better with existing markets or by creating completely new ones [9,15]. Further, brands that connect to consumers on a deeper level result in higher brand loyalty [14]. Knowing your end-users - and addressing them in the right way - can result in attitudinal and behavioral change [10,14] and designed experiences can have such an impact that they are remembered over time [11].

Table 2. List of experience design constituents

Topics	Explanation
(1) Context	Acknowledging of the importance of context when designing for experience.
(2) Narrative	Sensitivity of how design is given meaning in everyday life.
(3) Democratic	Increased participation and influence of different stakeholders
(4) Engagement	Engaging our bodily sensitivities when interacting with design.
(5) Respect	Acknowledging people’s intrinsic needs and desires.
(6) Strategic	Aligning designed experiences with instrumental goals.

3.2. Experience design process

This theme involves the experience design process. Topics range from the inherent uncertainty involved in the design process, how to include user information and the value of using model and prototypes. The topics are listed in Table 4 and explained in more detail below.

(1) **Iterative.** Most interviewees expressed that they conduct design research processes that are iterative [9,10,11]. As one interviewee mentioned, “design activity is not a linear process. It can best be described as *chaordic*; a process characterized by reflecting on design action, reflecting on artifacts and people’s responses in several design cycles [12].” Thus, designers are involved in dialogue and such processes often involve “finding opportunities instead of solving pre-defined problems [12].” Another interviewee commented, “although a structured design process allows control it does not result in greatness. This requires artistic quality [15].” In general, the beginning of such processes result in a diverse range of models having low resolution, involving less diversity of models having higher resolution in later stages of the process [11]. It is further

important to guard one’s autonomous design space, which is the zone of freedom within the restrictions imposed by external forces (client demands, technological possibilities, end-user considerations, etc.) [11].”

(2) **Unpredictable.** Experience designs processes can be unpredictable, especially during the initial stages. Many interviewees expressed that this is an issue for clients, and design consultancy agencies deal with this in their own way. For instance, two interviewees mentioned that everything, “is planned in pretty fine detail beforehand by setting clear goals and expectations [9]” and notifying the client as soon as possible when shifting from expectations (i.e., expectation management) [10,15]. Three interviewees mentioned, that there are many moments of contact with clients and updates on project development are given frequently [11,13,15]. As one interviewee mentioned, “sometimes a pilot study is conducted, which tackles most of the uncertainties [13]” and when starting projects “interviews are conducted to investigate the viewpoints of all stakeholders [15].” In this way, expectations are made clear and potential conflicts are identified beforehand.

(3) **User insights.** Experience design relies on user insights. “Start from the life-world of end-users for whom you are designing [12]”, “explore people’s feelings and attitudes [9]” and “opinions and beliefs [13].” Means in which subjective user information (experiences) and objective user information (behavior) is gathered differs at different stages of the design process. At the start of a design process, user insights are explored in order to identify design opportunities. User information is gathered on-site for instance, through contextual inquiries and user observations [9,15]. At intermediate stages of a design process user information is used to fine-tune design proposals generating new user insights. Information is gathered in the studio or gathered on-site for instance, through workshops [9,14] and walkthroughs with prototypes [9]. At later stages of a design process high fidelity prototypes (or production ready designs) are used to validate user information through classical usability testing techniques often carried out in a lab [15]. See Table 3 for an overview of the different techniques applied, type of information gathered, and their uses at the different stages in the design process.

Table 3. List of techniques that interviewees use to obtain user information at different stages of the design process

Technique	Type of information	Exploration	Generation	Validation
Fly on the wall	o	•		
Contextual inquiry	o	•		
Context mapping	s+o	•		
Diaries / Probes	s	•		
Looking over the shoulder	o	•	•	
Extreme users	s+o	•	•	
Focus groups	s	•	•	
Walkthroughs (talk-aloud)	s+o		•	
Workshops & co-creation	s+o		•	
Interviewing / questionnaires	s	•	•	•
Classical usability testing	s+o			•

Subjective information (s) / objective information (o)

(4) **Models.** In experience design, physical models are a means to “intervene with reality [12]” as one interviewee noted. Models and prototypes vary in fidelity and can have different functions. Examples of low fidelity prototypes are wire-frame models and physical models of foam that are used to explore and generate experience. Examples of high fidelity prototypes are interactive prototypes and “fit and finished models [15]” that are often used to validate experience. These high fidelity models are also valuable for experience generation

but two interviewees mentioned that it remains tedious to create interactive models early in the design process [9,15].

(5) **Empathy tools.** Empathy-tools allow an empathic connection with end-users without them being present. This is useful since “it takes a lot of time to find the right persons which can act as informants and participants [9].” Moodboards are used to understand and communicate concepts and narratives on an emotional level [11]. Personas, which are vivid representations of end-users, allow designers to connect with their personalities hereby helping them anticipate needs, preferences, and motivations. Further, end-to-end usage scenarios allow designers to address detail in anticipated use [13,14] and should include “non-glamorous moments [15].” Extreme users are valuable when actually involving end-users in the design process. Due to their “unconventional ways of thinking and working [15]” many insights can be obtained with a limited number of participants. Living personas are people that fit with a specific target-group (selected based upon personal characteristics) and are instructed to act out predefined scenarios in-situ, which can be compared to “type-casting combined with method-acting [11].”

Table 4. Topics part of experience design process

Topics	Explanation
(1) Iterative	Experience design involves multiple design cycles.
(2) Unpredictable	Ways of dealing with the inherent unpredictability in design research processes.
(3) User insights	Techniques to gather user insights at different stages of the design process.
(4) Models	Ways to use models and prototypes at different stages of the design process.
(5) Empathy tools	Creating empathy with end-users and use-contexts without making contact directly.

3.3. Experience design expertise

This theme involves experience design expertise. Topics range from the inherently multidisciplinary nature of experience design, the demands placed upon teamwork and communication skills as well as the overall attitude needed to design for experience successfully. Topics are listed in Table 6 and are described in more detail below.

(1) **Multidisciplinary.** Experience design is inherently multidisciplinary, “nowadays design challenges are too complex to be tackled by an individual [12].” Design teams harbor different disciplines and specialists are hired in for specific tasks at hand [12,13]. During the interviews a variety of disciplines were mentioned (see Table 5): Communication design allows the embodiment of ideas in (mostly visual based) interactive media: Human scientists understand experience and have the skill “to read between the lines while engineers create the hardware and software enabling the envisioned experiences [13].” Interaction design, industrial design and architecture require cross-disciplinary thinking and include most of the competencies mentioned above in their curricula. Branding and marketing are similar from a business perspective.

Table 5. Mentioned disciplines involved in experience design

Categories	Disciplines
(1) Design (product)	industrial design / product design / interaction design / game design
(2) Architecture	environmental design / interior design
(3) Communication design	user interface design / interactive media design / web design / visual design / graphic design
(4) Engineering	software engineering / mechanical engineering
(5) Human sciences	cognitive psychology / social & behavioural science / cultural anthropology / communication science
(6) Specialists	scenario writing / play writing / text editors / lighting specialist / artists / illustrators / audiovisual content creators / audio designers / psychotherapists / physicians
(7) Business science	commercial psychology / branding / marketing
(8) Management	creative leadership / project management

(2) **Teamwork and communication.** Given the multidisciplinary nature of experience design, knowing how to communicate with different disciplines [11,13] and “speaking the different jargons [9]” is important. Team members should adopt a cooperative attitude and big egos can be a disadvantage [10,11]. Further, people should be “inquisitive about developments in other disciplines [11]” in order to see the overall trends in the field. In relation to clients, one should be able to persuade and motivate clients for design proposals since clients often give a go-ahead based on a vision [13]. Managing experience design processes requires an understanding of the field, effective project management, clear communication [13,15] and the ability to operate in networks of expertise [14].

(3) **Human interest.** For experience design it is important to have an interest in people [11] and to be able to create an empathic understanding of them [10,11]: “Being able to acknowledge human nature and change perspectives [14].” Having an interest for the human senses [14] and material culture [13]. It further helps when experience designers have attained a level of psychological maturity [13] and have developed keen observation skills in order to see how people interact with design [9, 12].

(4) **Design Thinking.** Experience design requires design thinking. People should be creative and dare to breakaway from social conventions. Three interviewees mentioned the ability to combine analytical skills with intuition [11,12,13]. Being able to think conceptually and translate them into form [12,13]. Being able to create the right prototype for the right question [11] and designing exhibitions requires spatial insight as well as an understanding of narratives [13].

Table 6. Topics part of experience design expertise

Topics	Explanation
(1) Multidisciplinary	Experience design projects involve a variety of disciplines.
(2) Teamwork and communication	Experience design requires multidisciplinary teamwork and communication.
(3) Human interest	Experience designers require an interest in human nature.
(4) Design thinking	Experience design requires design thinking.

3.4. Experience design clients

This theme involves experience design clients. Topics range from clients' needs favoring an experience design approach as well as clients' awareness of experience design and promotional activities that design consultancy agencies undertake to increase it. The topics are listed in Table 7 and are described in more detail below.

(1) **Needs.** An experience design approach is valuable when clients want to profit from new markets or services (i.e., disruptive innovations). For example, when “introducing newly (patented) technologies to the market [9]” or when “introducing new public buildings (such as museums or learning centers) to the general public [13].” By using experiential models (described earlier in this paper) people’s opinions and attitudes can be explored beforehand hereby increasing the chance of success, and thus saving a client time and money [9]. Experience design is also valued when clients want to improve existing products and services (i.e., incremental innovations). For instance by testing an already developed concept in terms of strengths and weaknesses [9]. Further, design consultancy agencies discover that clients consider qualitative user insights more satisfactory than quantitative descriptions of customer-satisfaction. This was nicely illustrated by one of the interviewees: “What does a score of seven ‘mean’ for our organization [14]?”

(2) **Awareness.** Clients are aware of the benefit of taking end-users’ experiences seriously [10,11,15], especially in the medical domain [9]. However, a common frame of reference given the variety of interpretations when clients are confronted with the term experience design [10]. In larger companies, product managers surprisingly know little about their end-users, “their aim is to push products into the market and have as less products returned as possible [15].” Also, marketing and engineering departments of larger companies can be divided in whom their end-users really are [11,15]. Actually making contact with these end-users serves as a mirror, allowing companies to let go of unrealistic attachments to solutions [11]. Clients need persuasion to adopt an experience design approach since design is often interpreted in a narrow sense (creating nice product appearances) [15]. Sometimes this awareness is assessed before a project starts by performing maturity checks [11] or by facilitating workshops [14,15].

(3) **Promotion.** The interviewees mentioned different ways in which awareness of experience design is promoted. Newsletters and quarterly magazines are sent out to clients and designers to present them new visions and approaches [14,15]. Also websites and blogs are used to promote awareness [15], for instance “by collecting knowledge, finding examples and conducting interviews about user experience [11].” Interviewees also mentioned taking part in conferences, giving lectures at schools and universities [14,15] and joining societal platforms [15]. Two interviewees mentioned the benefit of creating alliances with other design consultancy agencies; sharing knowledge to learn how others do it in the field [9] while at the same time experiencing the tension between disclosure and advantage [10]. Further, these kinds of alliances require the commitment of “a couple of enthusiasts who want to pull the cart [11].” Something that is difficult to attain since priority is given to everyday practice.

Table 7. Topics part of experience design clients

Categories	Disciplines
(1) Needs	Clients’ needs in relation to experience design.
(2) Awareness	Clients’ awareness of experience design and its value for industry.
(3) Promotion	Activities promoting awareness of experience design.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Experience design constituents

Experience design is advanced by investigating the different experience design constituents. One could ask the following questions: Which contextual factors (e.g., physical and social circumstances, time of use) are most influential with respect to the desired experience of a product or service and how can we apply this knowledge in design? Which psychological factors (e.g. personal histories, attitudes and beliefs) mold artifacts into experienced narratives? Which sensory channels are important given certain communication purposes and how does combining different senses add to the quality of an experience? What do people find intrinsically valuable and how does this intrinsic value relate to business goals? The following activities can be envisioned to strengthen experience design practice.

- Identify contextual factors, which can strengthen or weaken a desired experience. This knowledge can be used to guide design choices but can also be used in the creation of context-aware products and services.
- Identify psychological characteristics of target groups (cultural backgrounds, shared histories and value systems) that influences how artifacts are perceived and are given meaning.
- Identify correlations between experience (sensations, perceptions and emotions) and human behavior (motivations, action-tendencies and movement).

4.2 Experience design process

Experience design practice is advanced by optimizing the design process. One could ask the following questions: How are highly iterative design processes managed best; how can it be planned out beforehand? Which mechanisms can be put into place that allows various stakeholders (end-users, clients, technologists, etc.) to monitor and influence the design process without placing too many demands upon the design consultancy agencies? When in the design process is end-user input valued most and what characterizes this input? How much of actual user involvement can be replaced successfully by empathy tools hereby reducing the amount of effort in selecting and managing end-user participation? How can interactivity be implemented early on in the design process and connect to technological platforms? The following activities can be envisioned to make experience design processes more effective and efficient:

- Develop procedures and communication tools that support clients' monitoring needs without burdening the design team.
- Develop prototyping techniques in which the interactivity of products and services are made experiential (and contextual) in early stages of the design process.
- Explore new empathy tools and validate their effectiveness by comparing them to end-user involvement.

4.3 Experience design expertise

Experience design practice is advanced by bringing people together with the right expertise and mindset. One could ask the following questions: How can mutual understanding and respect be promoted in multidisciplinary teams? How does this understanding influence teamwork and quality? Is social intelligence required to design for experience? The following activities can be envisioned to strengthen experience design expertise:

- Create awareness of the diversity of disciplines involved in experience design to understand their ways of working.
- Create activities that stimulate discussion between project members across different disciplines in alignment with project progression.
- Train bodily and emotional sensitivities in order to increase social intelligence.

4.4 Experience design clients

Experience design practice is advanced by promoting experience design as a means for innovation. Which jargons should be used to communicate with clients (depending upon the clientele) and how should experience design be positioned with respect to marketing and engineering? The following activities can be envisioned to strengthen business for experience design:

- Build models and frameworks for experience that connect:
(1) context, (2) body, (3) experience, (4) behavior and (5) business.
- Translate these models into tools that help in client communication (insight and persuasion).
- Promote experience design as an innovation strategy by highlighting the usefulness of combining qualitative insights with design solutions.

5. Conclusion

Results show that areas can be identified that advance experience design as a practice. From an academic perspective, researchers may see how current research on user experience relates to practices in industry. Various researchers are already investigating some of the issues raised by the participants but researchers may be inspired to explore other topics as well. From an industrial perspective, design consultancy agencies may connect to academia to strengthen the theoretical foundations of their practice or involve academia in the development of new methods and tools.

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